

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF TEACHER AND STUDENT STATUS ON THE BASE OF NATIONAL VALUES IN MODERN TEACHER'S ACTIVITY

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Abstract. *The feature of pedagogical guidance to students' extracurricular work is not only in the classroom, but also through social organizations, in the classroom and outside of school, through various activities, by directly involving students in technical creativity and agricultural experimentation, and in the Master-Apprentice system.*

The article highlights the issues of professional values, connection of values to personality structure, formation and strengthening of professional and moral behavior in the implementation of professional activities.

Keywords: *value, attention, attitude, culture, activity, goal, result, exhibition.*

Introduction

It is necessary to help students to properly organize extracurricular time and use it wisely for recreation. The deep inner essence of all forms of curricular and extracurricular work is to actively involve students in socially useful activities, to encourage their initiative and independence, and to develop their individual interests, inclinations and abilities. The feature of pedagogical guidance to students' extracurricular work is not only in the classroom, but also through social organizations, in the classroom and outside of school, through various activities, by directly involving students in technical creativity and agricultural experimentation, and in the Master-Apprentice system.

In order to ensure the implementation of the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 30, 2019 "On measures to improve the system of involving young people in the field of science and supporting their initiative" PQ - 4433, to realize the creative, intellectual and entrepreneurial potential of young people today, The necessary conditions are being created for the introduction of innovative ideas, projects and technologies into production, the promotion of innovative activities of talented students, young scientists and entrepreneurs, and the strengthening of the integration of science, education and production [1].

Researcher G. Gafurov listed the following manifestations of national values:

- 1) natural values;
- 2) economic values;
- 3) socio-political values;
- 4) moral values;
- 5) moral values [12].

For example, "Our ancestors, along with teaching science, instilled in our children the national, spiritual and moral values that are passed down from generation to generation" [16]. "The

majority of Uzbeks... prioritize the safety of close people and neighbors. This is the highest spiritual value, the jewel of the human heart [13].

Method

Conducting the teacher-student system based on national values is of great importance in the activity of a modern teacher. The main goal of establishing and improving the mentor-apprentice system is to provide students - young people with meaningful knowledge and professional skills, to follow the path of their mentors, and to ensure that in the future they will be knowledgeable in their field and spiritually healthy. In order to carry out this process continuously, it is necessary to raise the apprentice's profession to the level of art, to continue the training and work of the teachers while remaining faithful to our national values and traditions [2].

Professional culture is carried out in parallel with the process of professional development. If this process is successful, attitude towards the profession and interest in it will develop. If the profession satisfies and fulfills the needs of the individual or can be a means of achieving one's goal, then the profession becomes a value.

At the initial stage of professional activity, professional values are not included in the general activity system, they are manifested only at the level of expectation and imagination. We can call this the initial value. They are very loose and will not be clear. Professional practice and professional experience begin to form as soon as value researchers begin to perform professional activities. As a person enters this process, he makes a correction and strengthening of the sphere of value. Oriented values can become professional values if the "experiment" on professional values is successful and the individual has a positive attitude to the components of professional activity. If it is the other way around, the oriented values are broken and broken, reshaped, but not as originally formed, but restored through experience.

Connecting values to the personality structure helps to form professional moral behavior, to implement, strengthen or confirm specific professional activities. In other words, the implementation of professional activity is a factor of formation and strengthening of professional and moral behavior. Values are a set of people, relationships, situations, material things and spiritual wealth that have prestige, attention, respect, influence among people in society.

The profession unites specific groups of people and subgroups within them into one group at a time. Based on professional activity and lifestyle, it is attached to one or another professional group. In accordance with the world and based on the place in this world, commonality is selected within social and professional groups. The more "solidarity" there is in professional groups, the more common the views, beliefs, values, and rules of behavior of all group members. "Professional culture", "professional ethics", "professional honor" and "professional spirit" exist in such communities built on the ideas of solidarity and restraint.

Defining the professional culture as a phenomenon, we propose as a methodological basis: professionally oriented, competent, axiological and active, and as a main principle - the principle of development. It allows to systematize a number of developments, theoretical and empirical data from different sources.

Professional culture is a unity of worldly and special knowledge, qualities, skills, feelings, value orientations of a person, which are manifested during professional activity and ensure high level of efficiency. The general and professional culture of the specialist, which will be needed in the future activity, is related to his training, which increases and improves the quality of the achieved result.

By professional culture, we understand, first of all, the system (professional status) of a specialist for performing production tasks in a professional group. The implementation of professional activity provides for the specialist's choice of professional tasks. This choice is usually associated with professional culture and ensures the continuity and integrity of professional activity.

Results and discussion

Thus, the professional culture of a specialist can be manifested at three levels:

The first level is the acquisition of professional knowledge, skills and qualifications at the level of competence.

The second level is self-development in professional activity, as well as application of knowledge, skills and abilities in professional activity.

The third level - professional activity and professional development are considered at the level of value (ie, excellent performance of professional activity, level of professional skill).

When analyzing professional culture as a holistic acmeological phenomenon and consultative influence, the value-oriented aspect is relevant. All human activity is valuable with its process and result, it allows good relations of the surrounding people, defining its place in society.

Professional characteristics and its factors influence the formation of the professional culture of a future specialist. Objective and subjective, more or less important, personal and social can be distinguished from them. The objective effect shows global traditions in education, socio-philosophical problems of culture, the state of the educational system and the quality of general education services, the prestige of the profession in society.

When analyzing professional culture as a holistic acmeological phenomenon and consultative influence, the value-oriented aspect is relevant. All human activity is valuable with its process and result, it allows good relations of the surrounding people, defining its place in society. The content of valuable referrals has its own independent research base.

The second aspect of professional culture is a valuable dynamic aspect. Its importance is that it is independent, it can be easily and quickly assimilated if the culture is changing, the culture with new goals, values, rules and prohibitions can be changed through consultation. Thus, the dynamic aspect of value involves independent psychological learning and can change the collective culture.

The attitude of science to the acmeological aspect of the profession is not new today. More attention is paid to scientific views and approaches. Two opposite approaches to the problem of formation of professional values and professional ethical behavior can be distinguished.

On the one hand, the supporters of the personal development approach in professional activity (Klimov, Markova, Zeer) study the stages of professional skill development and completion, and do not connect them with the dynamics of professional values development. Also, there is no field defined as professional values in any classification of the person and professionally oriented structure.

On the other hand, proponents of the acmeological approach affirm primary professional spirituality as a response to professional self-awareness. Also, in the process of social experience and personal development, a worldview structure is formed, in which the attitude to the profession and professional activity is based on the value aspect.

In our opinion, these two approaches need to be clarified and corrected. The essence of the question goes back to the essence of value. By addressing this question in more depth, the nature of the problem can be clarified and justified.

In general, the justification of values is based on the psychology of the phenomenon. In order to understand the object as a value, the subject needs a specific sensitivity, positive feelings formed as a result of interaction between the subject and the object, a unique holistic subjective mental state. For a person, values are his state of mind. Therefore, value is the ability of the object to satisfy the requirements of the subject, as well as the mental state of their interaction.

In this way, value relations include the object of the external world and one's own personal value structure as the inner world of a person. A person chooses an object of value and creates forms of personal value to create a positive state, to satisfy his needs and interests.

In the field of values, the values related to professional activity have a special place, these are the most important professional values in human life. In fact, when it comes to the formation of values, criteria and rules for the organization of employee development in organizations, these values (processes, activities, rituals) must be practically integrated.

Through organizational culture, any organization is considered as a subject of professional activity, an object of evaluation. In this way, the value of the organization is equated with professional values in the way of its goal.

When it comes to the formation of organizational values, no one talks about the formation of professional values, in which emphasis is placed on professional activity and professional behavior, which instead defines the professional moral side of the activity.

Values are formed in direct relationship with the object, as well as in professional activity in this field. As a result of this relationship, a positive result is accumulated, a positive emotional effect is achieved. The relationship is demonstrative, meaningful, the correspondence of meanings can be physical, moral, virtual. In all cases, a person participates in this process. His direct participation is necessary.

In the process of professional education, contact with the object is related to the elements of professional activity:

- educational process;
- environmental factors;
- pedagogical technologies;
- the person of the teacher;
- educational conditions (as working conditions);
- professional knowledge;
- competencies and others.

The object of valued attitude is distant; the mediator introduces personal semantics into the subjective meaning, shaping the process of association with the object (for example, I like medicine, but who teaches it how). Thus, certain difficulties are encountered in the formation of values or they are not formed at all.

Summary

On the basis of national values, the status of Master and Student is of great importance in the modern teacher's activity, and it is necessary to constantly inculcate professional values and professional culture of a specialist in students. When personal values are integrated with

organizational values, a person realizes value when he develops professionally and socially. The teacher teaches his student the national spiritual heritage, the structure of values, the historical heritage and historical memory of the Juma, cultural monuments, artifacts, ancient manuscripts, scientific achievements and masterpieces of philosophical thought, works of art and national literature, moral qualities, religious values, traditions. It is necessary to constantly teach customs, traditions and rituals, enlightenment, education, etc.

Values are divided into the following according to their content, importance, and characteristics:

1. Material values.
2. Spiritual values.
3. Socio-political values.

Values are divided into the following types according to their essence:

1. The highest value is a person and his life;
2. Natural values - land, water, underground, air, forest, plants, animal world and others;
3. "Second nature" or material values - wealth, plants, factories, transport, equipment, houses, delicacies, that is, things created by human labor;
4. Cultural and spiritual values - education, education, medical care, heritage, language, literature, art, craft products, memorials, etc.;
5. Socio-political values. Freedom, stability, brotherhood, peace.

Conclusion

From what has been discussed and analyzed above it can be inferred that on the basis of national values, it is considered necessary for a teacher to inculcate professional values in his student. In this case, the subject's active-positive entry into the organizational process is considered a factor in the development of professional values. In our opinion, in this case, the organization can form a professional culture with the help of the development of special programs, which should include the following steps:

1. Adaptability, the organization must establish a positive relationship with the individual.
2. Diagnostic, its purpose is to establish the level of compatibility of value structures and acceptance of common values by the parties.
3. Developer, whose goal is to ensure active communication between the two parties. The organization should be concerned with professional activity, initiative, development of professional competence and confirmation of value orientations of the specialist and should focus on it (using all available forms).
4. Corrector, whose goal is to bring all the process participants close to each other.
5. Determinant, its purpose is to strengthen the common value system and build the perspective of the professional culture of the organization and the specialist.

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